

Destination Earth

Building a highly accurate digital twin of the Earth

Stay informed of key milestones, events and engagement opportunities by subscribing to the DestinE community

destination-earth.eu

TECHNOLOGY PROVIDERS

Carrying out a dual role in the DestinE ecosystem, both contributing solutions and expertise to DestinE and leveraging DestinE's capabilities to develop added value technologies and applications.

DestinE is a flagship initiative of the European Commission that is developing a digital twin of the Earth to support climate change and extreme weather events adaptation and mitigation strategies. This novel information system will provide unprecedented levels of detail, quality and interactivity, to support policymakers to better respond and adapt to environmental challenges posed by extreme events and climate change.

By supporting the development and implementation of DestinE with solutions and expertise, technology providers will reach new markets, gain access to a wealth of technology and data and be able to expand and enhance their products and services.

Amplifying innovation across technological domains

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Simulation and modelling software

Cybersecurity and data privacy

Cloud to edge continuum

High performance computing

IOT and remote sensing

...and more!

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DestinE will foster the implementation of the EU Digital Strategy and the Green Deal target of a climate-neutral Europe by 2050 by leveraging digital technology to enable accurate and actionable adaptation strategies and mitigation measures to:

Anticipate both natural disasters and man-made environmental damage.

Enable investigating what if scenarios to understand consequences of adaptation choices and explore possible future evolutions of our planet.

Understand the socio-economic effects of climate change.

Help communities adapt to climate change related challenges.

Destination Earth Components

DestinE Platform

User's entry point to the DestinE system, offering evidence-based decision-making tools, applications and services, based on an open, flexible, and secure cloud-based computing infrastructure.

Data Lake

Data access harmonisation of digital twins data and federated providers such as ESA, EUMETSAT, ECMWF, Copernicus and many other sources. Big data processing capabilities provided to allow computing in proximity to the data.

Digital Twins and Digital Twin Engine

Digital twins of different aspects of the earth system based on the fusion of cutting-edge simulations and observations, orchestrated by the Digital Twin Engine that provides a software infrastructure for digital twin data access, workflows and interoperability and data production and handling.

